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Conflict And Conflict Management In Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area: A Study Of ONELGA Security, Planning And Advisory Committee

A. Egobueze¹; E. I. Amadi² & F. N. Chukwumah³

^{1,2,3}**Department of Political Science
Faculty of Social Sciences
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

The study examined the impact of OSPAC on conflict and conflict resolution in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State. To achieve this goal, four objectives were established in accordance with four research questions and hypotheses. A mixed research method was employed, incorporating both survey and descriptive techniques. Questionnaires and interviews were utilized as tools and methods for data collection. Both primary and secondary data were gathered and utilized simultaneously. The study employed cluster and simple random sampling techniques. A sample size of four hundred individuals was determined using Taro Yarmane's formula and analyzed through descriptive statistics, simple percentages, and frequency distributions. The Chi-square test was used to confirm the hypotheses. To provide a theoretical framework for the increase in conflict and insecurity in ONELGA, the study adopted the social conflict theory. In explaining the selection of OSPAC as a conflict management agency in ONELGA, the community implant theory was utilized. The research revealed, among other findings, that OSPAC plays a variety of roles, such as collaborating with security forces to combat the activities of cultists, drug traffickers, and criminals in ONELGA. OSPAC employed various strategies, including engaging with other vigilante groups, using light weapons, and setting up roadblocks and patrols to manage conflicts in ONELGA. The study recommended, among other suggestions, that the state government should take on the financial responsibility of OSPAC. It should also encourage other local governments to establish their own vigilante groups under the same name as seen in Etche and Emohua Local Government Areas. Security agencies should be granted full autonomy to oversee the operations of vigilante groups to prevent political interference.

Keywords: Advisory Committee, Conflict, Conflict Management, Planning and Security

INTRODUCTION

The surge in violent crime in Nigeria has spurred citizens to explore alternative security measures or resort to self-help strategies in order to combat crime and thwart the activities of dishonest individuals and troublemakers, as well as to bring them to justice. Rivers State has witnessed a significant rise in kidnapping cases, with perpetrators demanding exorbitant ransoms. Furthermore, communities are grappling with a myriad of criminal activities including cult operations, abductions, illicit oil theft, among others (Eze and Onyishi, 2020). The repercussions of these criminal activities are severe, leading to the closure of numerous businesses and causing investors to seek safer locations. Therefore, in order for

communities to flourish, it is imperative to establish and maintain peace and security, as peace serves as the foundation for development, while insecurity and conflict serve as impediments to progress.

Research and observations have unveiled a myriad of criminal activities in Rivers State, particularly in the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni local government area. It has been established that crime is closely linked to poverty and a high rate of unemployment. Consequently, it can be inferred that crises and insecurity exacerbate developmental challenges. An incident was documented where a pregnant woman was callously thrown into a water-filled well, and more than 26 individuals lost their lives between 2008 and 2019 in the Ibaa Community. This resulted in a dearth of skilled labor and tarnished the reputation of the affected community. The root causes of this insecurity can be attributed to failures in leadership, poverty, power struggles for chieftaincy positions, and involvement in cult activities (Amadi 2020; Amadi & Nwogu, 2020).

Furthermore, it was observed in certain communities within the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA that businesses and residents were compelled to relocate to safer areas for security, consequently draining these insecure areas of financial resources that could have been utilized for their development. The incidents of insecurity in the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA saw a significant surge from 2012 to 2014. According to the Rivers State Conflict Bulletin 2021, in February 2014, an APC chairman in one of the wards was tragically assassinated, and in May 2014, a clash between rival cult groups resulted in the deaths of more than ten individuals in the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni area. Additionally, it was reported that a confrontation between two armed youths led to the loss of three lives in the same region. In January 2015, a violent clash erupted between the Deebam and Deywell cult factions, resulting in the deaths of three cult members. This escalation in communal tensions prompted a mass exodus of residents to more peaceful communities and LGAs.

In light of the escalating situation in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni, numerous young individuals within the locality turned to nefarious activities such as abduction, theft, armed robbery, and online fraud commonly referred to as 'yahoo-yahoo'. Consequently, a multitude of infrastructures and amenities, including the Social Development Institute situated in the LGA headquarters, fell victim to vandalism at the hands of unruly individuals. As these acts of insecurity and criminality persist, many have pointed fingers at the police and other governmental security agencies, citing their perceived ineffectiveness in fulfilling their duties (Adiele, 2021). The issues stemming from the failure of security agencies to combat crime include rampant corruption among security personnel, inadequate remuneration, substandard equipment, and unsanitary working conditions that hinder the effectiveness of security operations in the nation. With these challenges at play, there has been a surge in criminal activities that not only impede the social fabric but also hinder the political and economic progress of Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni local government areas.

As the prevalence of criminal activities escalates, the residents of Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni have chosen to implement self-vigilance measures for security purposes, taking over the responsibilities of the Onelga Security, Planning and Advisory Committee (OSPAC) vigilante security and other security mechanisms (Emeodu & Elem, 2020; Adiele, 2021). Despite numerous studies highlighting the surge in crimes in Rivers State and recommending a community-based security approach, none have delved into the role of the Onelga Security, Planning and Advisory Committee (OSPAC) vigilante group in crime prevention. In light of this context, this research aims to explore the effectiveness of the Onelga Security, Planning and Advisory Committee (OSPAC) vigilante group in controlling crime within selected communities in the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study is aimed at assessing the role of OSPAC in conflict and security management in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State. The specific objectives of this study include, to:

- i.** determine the roles of OSPAC in security interventions in ONELGA.
- ii.** examine the conflict management strategies utilized by OSPAC in conflict management in ONELGA.

This objectives are in line with two research questions posed as follows:

- i.** What were the roles of OSPAC in security interventions in ONELGA?

1.3 What were the conflict management strategies utilized by OSPAC in conflict management in ONELGA?

Theoretical Framework

The social conflict theory was adopted as a philosophical framework for this paper and it originated by Karl Marx in his early work, known as the dialectical materialist interpretation of history (1818-1883). He posits that since the inception of societies, individuals have been entangled in various forms of conflict. Conflict can be described as the plausible confrontation or competition between individuals with divergent needs, ideas, beliefs, values, or objectives. Numerous academics have unanimously concurred that conflict is unavoidable. However, the outcomes of conflict are unpredictable. Thus, conflict has the potential to intensify and result in unproductive consequences, while simultaneously, in the midst of conflict, there are individuals who directly benefit despite the perilous and destructive nature of conflict.

Dickson (2021) elucidates that conflict theories focus on power differentials, such as class conflict, and typically juxtapose historically prevalent ideologies – positing it as a macro level analysis of societal strife. The social conflict theory, attributed to Karl Marx, has emerged as a significant component in both sociological and political realms worldwide. Nevertheless, the traditional conflict theory is a sociological construct that encompasses the social, political, or material disparities within a social group critical of the overarching socio-political system, diverging from structural functionalism and ideological conservatism. Ewetan and Imeokparia (2021) argue that the foundational ideas of conflict theory can be traced back to early philosophy, citing Han Fei Tzu (280 - 233 BC) and other ancient Chinese philosophers who posited that humans are inherently feeble and indolent, contending that the only means of control is through punitive measures. The fundamental premise underlying this notion is that society can be governed through the establishment of a punitive system to maintain order.

However, Simmel (1964) referenced in the contributions of Ibok and Arikpo (2019) to the theory, which was primarily popularized by Polybius, an ancient Greek philosopher (205-125 BC), whose focus was on the Roman Republic. Simmel characterized people as akin to herds of animals. Recognizing the inherent vulnerabilities of humanity, individuals seek alliances to establish communities where the most powerful and courageous individuals will assume leadership roles while others will follow suit. Polybius elucidated that societies undergo transformation and evolve into monarchies based on principles of justice and legitimate authority. It is incumbent upon monarchs to maintain peace and social order. However, despite this weighty responsibility, monarchs are not immune to the frailties that afflict mankind, and as such, tendencies towards corruption and injustice can manifest within monarchies as well. Swanstrom and Weissman (2005), as cited by Ifeanyi (2020, (p.35), posited that "when tyranny becomes intolerable, the elite members of society will devise strategies to overthrow the monarchy. The general populace will rally behind these new leaders due to their promise of increased liberty and equality".

Hence, the cycle will continue when the new leader restricts some of the liberties and equality of the population. Therefore, Polybius argues that the only way to disrupt this cycle is to establish a government that combines the best qualities of monarchies, aristocracies, and democracies, similar to the Roman regime. It is noteworthy that many philosophers held similar beliefs about conflict and society. Conflict, as a sociological concept, was organized and thoroughly explained in the 19th and 20th Centuries, building upon the earlier contributions of individuals such as Polybius. Several sociologists have enriched the development of conflict theory, including Max Gluckman, John Rex, Lewis A. Coser, Randall Collins, Ralf Dahrendorf, Ludwig Gumplowicz, Vilfredo Pareto, and Georg Simmel. However, Karl Marx is widely recognized as the originator of conflict theory (Chambliss, 1973 cited by Ifeanyi 2020).

The theme of conflict theory in politics can be traced back to influential political thinkers such as Machiavelli and Thomas Hobbes, both of whom held a cynical view of humanity (Oberschall, 1978 as cited by Ifeanyi, 2020). Oberschall (1978) as cited by Ifeanyi (2020) highlighted that modern conflict theory transitioned from a rationalistic approach to an empirical investigation through the works of David Hume and Adam Ferguson. By treating conflict as an empirical reality, Hume laid the groundwork for the contemporary theory of political parties. Ferguson, on the other hand, expanded on these concepts to

provide a comprehensive explanation of political institutions and government, positing that they emerge from conflict.

Successive intellectuals have delineated diverse iterations of conflict theory; a prevailing motif posits that disparate social factions wield unequal influence, yet all contend for the same scarce resources. Conflict theory posits that society is not most aptly comprehended as a intricate system striving for balance, but rather as a realm of rivalry. Society comprises individuals engaged in competition for finite resources. Francis Abraham (1983) as referenced in Swanstrom and Weissmann (2005) notes that conflict theories are delimited to the interconnectedness between multiple units within society. Instances such as racial discord, class warfare, religious strife, labor strikes, demonstrations, student movements, revolutions, peasant revolts, and similar phenomena frequently serve as subjects of scrutiny.

The fundamental tenet of conflict theory is grounded in the belief that society and its components are in a perpetual state of flux albeit at varying rates; change and conflict are ongoing and thus constitute inherent facets of human society. This posits that society is not a stable system but a nebulous arrangement of imperfectly coordinated elements held together by the coercion of some and the subjugation of others. Conflict theory further postulates that society is a platform populated by animate, striving, and competing entities. Social conflicts are intrinsic to the very fabric of social organization; the dichotomy between exogenous and endogenous conflicts is relevant solely in an analytical context. Furthermore, the inherent prophecies of societal change vary in range, character, intensity, and speed; they may be latent or overt, gradual or cataclysmic (Wall & Callister, 1973 as cited by Ewetan and Imeokparia 2021).

Francis Abraham, as referenced in Swanstrom and Weissmann (2005) and cited by Ifeanyi (2020), posited that conflicts can be categorized into two main types: endogenous conflicts, such as conflicts related to values, authority, distribution of resources, and conflicts between individuals and society, and exogenous conflicts, which encompass wars, cultural invasions, and ideological conflicts. Abraham further noted that classical works on conflict theory identify two distinct traditions.

- i) The tradition of political philosophy concerning power relations. Noteworthy figures in this tradition consist of Machiavelli, Bodin, Hobbes, and Mosca. They have delved into the conflicts within the political sphere through the lens of power dynamics, with the state being the focal point of their analysis.
- ii) The tradition of competitive dynamics in classical economics. Key figures in this tradition encompass Adam Smith, Robert Malthus, and subsequent generations of economists. They have positioned economic rivalry as the central theme of their investigations.

Sociological conflict theory represents a merging of two distinct traditions, primarily focusing on the inequitable distribution of resources within society. Karl Marx is widely regarded as the preeminent figure in this field. Other notable contributors include C. Wright Mills, Ralf Dahrendorf, Lewis Coser, and Randall Collins, among others. In the context of this analysis, it can be postulated that the fundamental tenet of conflict theory posits that individuals and social groups engage in a struggle to maximize their access to finite resources that are both scarce and coveted by humanity. As a result of this scarcity, this struggle inevitably leads to conflict and cutthroat competition. These conflicts often precipitate changes within institutions and societies as various factions vie for dominance. The quintessence of conflict theory is perhaps best exemplified by the traditional "pyramid structure" in which the masses are subjugated by the bourgeoisie.

Hence, all establishments, monuments, regulations, and customs within society are structured to uphold and safeguard the prevailing beliefs. Conflict theorists have persistently contended that all factions within society originate as a result of discord. To delve deeper into this concept, Labor Unions, which are established to advocate for the welfare of workers, and Trade Organizations are embroiled in the struggle to maintain and safeguard the interests of these specific social classes. This group theory contrasts with functionalism, in which these factions fulfill a defined role in the progression of society. Within functionalism, these factions collaborate for the betterment of society. Conflict theory factions are in opposition to one another as they strive to advance their own interests and challenge the existing order.

In comprehending conflict theory, the rivalry among social classes plays a pivotal role. The ensuing are the fundamental assumptions of contemporary conflict theory:

Interactions: Human interactions give rise to discord.

Change: Conflict and transformation are customary and unavoidable in society.

Competition: The struggle for scarce resources (such as wealth, leisure, romantic partners, etc.) is inherent in all social circles. Competition, rather than consensus, is a defining feature of human relationships. If every individual possessed the necessary resources, conflict would cease to exist.

Structural Inequality: Disparities in authority and benefits are ingrained in all social frameworks. Resources are limited, and groups will perpetually vie for these resources.

Degree of Inequality: Inequality manifests in various degrees, with individuals possessing varying amounts of resources; hierarchies prevail.

Revolution: Macroscopic alterations transpire as a consequence of clashes between conflicting interests rather than through adaptation. These changes are frequently sudden and revolutionary as opposed to gradual and evolutionary.

The primary goal of the affluent is to amass greater wealth, while the middle class and underprivileged are continuously striving to enhance their living conditions. This dynamic can be interpreted as reflective of a society's ethical standards, shaping their perception of what constitutes deviant behavior. Anything that poses a threat to the authority of the elite is likely to be labeled as "deviant" or "morally objectionable." Conflict theory posits that social order is upheld through coercion and power dynamics, rather than through consensus and uniformity. In line with conflict theory, individuals in positions of wealth and influence seek to maintain their status through any means necessary, often resorting to oppressive tactics to suppress and subjugate the less fortunate. Conflict theory also attributes many pivotal historical developments, such as the advancement of democracy and civil liberties, to self-serving endeavors by the capitalist class to manipulate the masses, rather than a genuine pursuit of societal harmony. Central to conflict theory is the notion that societies and institutions operate with the primary objective of safeguarding the interests of the individual participants, leading to ongoing struggles to maximize personal gains, which invariably contribute to social transformation. Conflict theory has been applied to elucidate a broad spectrum of social phenomena, ranging from armed conflicts and revolutions, to economic disparities and discrimination, as well as instances of domestic abuse.

This theory provides a foundational understanding of the origins of conflict in Onelga, leading to the establishment of a neighborhood watch group known as the Onelga Security, Planning, and Advisory Committee (OSPAC). Karl Marx posits that throughout the history of societies, conflict has been an inherent aspect of human interaction. Conflict can be defined as a tangible struggle or competition between individuals with differing needs, ideas, beliefs, values, or objectives. It is widely accepted that conflict is an omnipresent and unavoidable element of human society due to the ongoing class struggle between the affluent and the impoverished. In societies where a distinct separation exists between those who possess wealth and control production means and those who struggle to survive and depend on the former, conflict is bound to arise. Onelga is characterized by a diverse population with various social strata, including Ogba, Egbema, and Ndoni, within the local government. This diversity alone provides a fertile ground for potential conflicts to arise.

This aligns with the premise of conflict theory, which posits that society should not be viewed as a intricate system seeking balance, but rather as a arena of competition. Within society, individuals vie for scarce resources. As noted by Francis Abraham (1983) and referenced in Swanstrom and Weissmann (2005), conflict theories focus on the interactions between different entities within society.

THEMATIC EVALUATION OF CONFLICT AND CONFLICT MANAGEMENT

Conflicts are intricate struggles that emerge among individuals or groups due to disparities in values, claims of status, or competition over scarce resources. As stated by the National Crime Prevention Council (NCPC) (2019), conflicting parties engage in disputes to uphold their values and assert their claims against others. Disagreements ensue when one faction feels that its interests are being adversely affected or influenced by the opposing faction. Nonetheless, Okonwko and Akpoghme (2020) posit that conflict is a subjectively perceived reality rather than an objective truth. Conversely, Amodu (2019) characterizes conflict as the divergence of perceived interests or beliefs where the aspirations of both

parties cannot be simultaneously achieved. This indicates that conflict arises from the conviction that the desires of both parties cannot be realized concurrently. Aspirations are often articulated as objectives, aims, or acceptable benchmarks. The perceived desirability of one party and its incongruity with the desirability of the other party contribute to the perception of conflict.

Nwogu and Obasi (2020) define conflict as divergences in interests among individuals or groups, which may stem from secular or non-secular, ethnic, ideological, or other factors that culminate in confrontations. These conflicts have the potential to escalate into wars, resulting in depopulation and devastation. Odufuwa (2020) perceives conflict as behavior aimed at obstructing the accomplishment of another individual's objectives. In essence, conflict emerges from conflicting actions and can manifest at the individual, group, or organizational level. Conflict arises whenever one's viewpoints or decisions are perceived as impeding or encroaching upon the objectives, wishes, or actions of others. Conflict can arise from various organizational factors, such as incompatible goals, disparities in interpreting information, negative emotions, differences in values and philosophies, or disputes over shared resources (Akpan and Isong, 2020).

Conflicts have long been pervasive in Nigerian society. Dada and Farounbi (2021) emphasize that the origins of conflicts in Nigerian society are multifaceted and deeply ingrained in a multitude of factors. These factors encompass disputes over incongruent objectives and interests, endeavors to seize authority or positions within society, disparities in ambitions, the quest for independence or control among various individuals or factions, insufficiency or scarcity of resources to fulfill the requirements of different segments, and breakdowns in communication, among various other catalysts.

Ali and Ojo (2021) categorize conflicts based on their causal factors. These encompass conflicts stemming from competition for control over scarce or finite resources, conflicts emanating from perceived threats to our value system, which may encompass our preferences, lifestyles, ideologies, or religious convictions, conflicts arising from internal and interpersonal discrepancies in terms of psychological requirements, and conflicts instigated by the manipulation of information to provoke individuals towards conflict or peace-building. The adverse impacts of conflicts on society are profound and immeasurable, underscoring the imperative for interventions to mitigate the prevalence of conflicts (Okogbule & Wosu, 2020).

Hence, conflict resolution strategies are essential for the management of conflicts within society. Conflict resolution refers to a process designed to diminish, eradicate, or conclude a conflict. It includes various undertakings such as mediation, negotiation, bargaining, and arbitration, all of which are categorized as conflict resolution techniques. Considering the substantial impact of conflict resolution in Nigerian society, the importance of traditional rulers as preservers of culture cannot be emphasized enough. They play a crucial role in fostering conflict resolution within their respective communities.

The current conflict faced by Nigerian society and the global community can indeed be regulated and controlled. The management of conflict varies in terms of causes, origins, and contexts. Conflict management, also known as conflict avoidance, involves devising strategies to prevent conflict whenever possible and taking swift and efficient action when it does arise. The underlying principle of conflict avoidance is the recognition that all facets of human personal and social interactions have the potential to generate conflict. As such, individuals, organizations, and society at large should be prepared to anticipate conflict and take steps to prevent it. Prevention of conflict entails establishing mechanisms to address it when it emerges and finding ways to resolve conflicts that have already escalated (Okunloye & Olokooba, 2021). It is only when the root cause of a conflict is clearly identified that viable alternative solutions can be proposed. Okunloye and Olokooba (2021) argue that the conflict management process is based on the understanding that all conflict scenarios have the potential to be harmful and detrimental to the objectives of an organization.

Conflict resolution can be carried out by the conflicting parties themselves or by a mediator. To transform the entire conflict scenario and address the destructive elements within the conflict process, it is essential for the opposing parties with conflicting goals to work towards sustainable resolutions. Okunloye and Olokooba (2021) emphasize that effective conflict management involves reducing disruptions caused by conflicts and reaching a solution that is both satisfactory and acceptable. They also highlight that

strategies for conflict settlement involve containing or limiting certain behaviors, while conflict resolution strategies focus on addressing the attitudes, circumstances, and behaviors of the parties involved. Therefore, it is imperative for organizations to have a diverse array of mechanisms in place to address and handle conflicts effectively.

Deliberately implementing essential mechanisms within an organization can facilitate the establishment of a conflict resolution framework. Oftentimes, intense conflicts can be mitigated by implementing conflict prevention strategies aimed at altering or substituting coercive actions. The conventional approach to conflict resolution within organizations should aim for the most effective methods of managing conflicts, by providing robust backing to a strategy capable of resolving conflicts in a satisfactory manner. It is important to note that conflict resolution may not always be the immediate result of an intervention. Ojewale (2021) highlights this fact:

The conventional approach to conflict resolution involves the utilization of supernatural forces. Despite the predominance of Muslims and Christians in Nigeria, traditional religious beliefs and rituals continue to hold significant sway. The realm of ancestors is seen as a continuation of the earthly realm, with supernatural powers being an integral component of the Nigerian belief system. Ancestors, both royal and non-royal, along with other deities and sacred sites, are believed to deliver definitive and just resolutions to disputes within and among communities (p.23).

This method of conflict resolution involves the use of spiritual intermediaries, such as kola nuts, libations, and offerings, to invoke the aid of deities in resolving disputes related to farms, land, and familial matters. According to Otite (1999) as cited in Ojewale (2021), the parties involved in such conflicts consider the resolutions reached through this method to be final and sanctioned by the divine. These agreed-upon terms are typically adhered to out of fear of severe consequences, such as death or incurable illnesses inflicted by the spirit world. As a result of the perceived supernatural intervention in conflict resolution, tempers are calmed, and weapons are set aside.

Another conventional method of conflict resolution involves the utilization of an elders' council, which stands as one of the most influential bodies in community-based governance due to its deeply ingrained cultural practices. Culture represents the authentic way of life of a specific group, encompassing their values, beliefs, and unique social structures. When disputes arise and the elders' council steps in, they are widely perceived as the most knowledgeable, impartial, and seasoned individuals who have gathered to provide decisive and unfiltered rulings on the matter at hand. These venerable elders are akin to the justices of the Supreme Court, and their decisions are deemed infallible. Although the traditional approach to conflict management persists, the credibility and prestige of such councils are now often underestimated. Various traditional institutions, including traditional rulers and chieftaincy structures, the General Assembly, the deities/shrines/chief priests' establishments, and the kinship and family systems, employ diverse strategies for conflict resolution, tailored to the specific needs of each community. What proves effective in one community may not necessarily be applicable in another.

Okwudili and Okoye (2021) posit that traditional methods of conflict resolution exhibit significant variation across societies, regions, and communities (p.6). The diversity in cultural practices and customs is evident not only in the global south but also in other parts of the world. Oladipo and Oluwafemi (2022, p.6) contend that “traditional approaches are inherently context-specific and do not possess universal applicability like modern or conventional methodologies. Even within the Niger Delta communities, the techniques employed by traditional institutions for conflict management and resolution differ from one community to another, particularly when considering the multitude of ethnic groups within the region. Nevertheless, many Niger Delta communities share similar traditional approaches, particularly in light of their shared historical background of oil exploration and exploitation.

The traditional institutions in Nigeria play a vital role in conflict resolution. Olaoba (2019) highlights that these institutions serve as the embodiment and guardian of the rich cultural heritage, norms, and values, acting as agents of development and, most importantly, as catalysts for change that must be preserved. In many post-independence African nations, the chieftaincy institution and traditional rulers have been viewed as obstacles to modernization and nation-building, leading to attempts to limit their influence in

local governance and national politics (Omodu, 2019). According to Onuoha (2019), a chief is defined as an individual elected or chosen in accordance with the customs and traditions of the community, officially recognized by the government, and therefore possessing authority to carry out specific functions either derived from tradition or assigned by the central government within designated areas. A significant aspect of this definition is the focus on the selection or election process, which is rooted in the community's traditions prior to government recognition, whether at the state or federal level.

The interconnectedness between these two entities stems from the necessity of collective effort for progress to occur. Therefore, it is incumbent upon the Chiefs to advocate for the establishment of developmental initiatives within their region. Oriola (2021) elucidated that the governance of local areas may face challenges if solely entrusted to democratic authorities, emphasizing the essential role of traditional institutions in fostering peace and advancement. The crux of the matter is that in order for progress to be achieved, all aspects of traditional institutions must align to drive development. This can be facilitated by providing the necessary backing, recognition, and encouragement to traditional institutions to effectively fulfill their duties. It is crucial to underscore that traditional institutions serve as custodians of the community's culture and heritage, thereby being attuned to the immediate needs of the local populace.

Similarly, Oyedele (2019) asserts that traditional institutions and native authorities, such as traditional rulers and the chieftaincy institution, wield substantial influence in the resolution of communal land conflicts. The author further highlights that chiefs, council of elders, age grades, general assemblies, deities, and shrines have collectively made pivotal decisions on crucial matters, including determining the nature and priority of development projects. Oyekanmi & Oyelaran-Oyeyinka (2021, (p.10) posit that "the traditional chieftaincy institution plays a vital role in structuring society by upholding cultural tenets such as norms, customs, beliefs, and values of the people".

During the colonial era, traditional institutions held significant influence in conflict resolution and continue to serve as the embodiment of both the political and emotional desires of the people. Colonialism not only brought an end to the African extended family structure, values, way of life, and religious beliefs but also disrupted the solid foundation for peace and sustainability. Riaz (2020) emphasizes the crucial role of the general assembly in managing, passing resolutions, and providing lasting solutions to social and communal conflicts within communities. According to Riaz (2020, p.6), the "General Assembly and the age grade play a vital part in resolving conflicts such as cultism, land disputes, and communal crises in rural areas". Additionally, Riaz (2020) asserts that age grades sometimes mobilize resources to fund important community projects that were damaged during crises, function as village law enforcement, and act as executive agents for the governing body of the town or community, enforcing penalties and collecting fines imposed by the unions (p.8).

Udochukwu & Egwuatu (2023) assert that within the Ohafia community, the age grades system, known as "Ndeuke," serves as a prominent social mechanism for peacebuilding and conflict resolution. They further emphasize the significant role played by the village General Assembly in managing and resolving crises. In a similar vein, Umoren (2019) argues that scholars have acknowledged the importance of age grades in maintaining the Ohafia social structure and serving as effective tools for resolving conflicts. Therefore, it can be deduced that both the village General Assembly and the age grade system continue to play vital roles in promoting peace and fostering social cohesion. Williams (2021) affirms that the practice of age grades in Nigeria, as well as the performances of the village General Assembly, have roots dating back to the pre-colonial era when the Igbo people incorporated them into their traditional political structures.

Within the framework of age grade and village General Assembly systems, males belonging to specific age cohorts were organized into distinct age groups and also established a General Assembly to facilitate peacebuilding, conflict resolution, and community development initiatives (Okoli, Agbo, Nwaiwu, Alaribe, Ozor, Alozie, Adonu, & Odu, 2020). The effectiveness of promoting peace, resolving conflicts, and preserving the cultural traditions of the community can be attributed to the efficiency, proactive nature, adaptability, and significance of the age grades and General Assemblies within African traditional society.

In a similar manner, Obasi and Nnamani (2015) argue that deities and ancestral shrines have been utilized to provide a lasting solution to cult activities in rural areas of Rivers State through the ritual pouring of libations to address the problem of cultism and its associated behaviors. This claim was supported by Obasi and Nnamani (2015) who assert, among other things, that the practice of swearing at ancestral shrines has proven effective in resolving conflicts in rural communities. Okoro (2019) suggests that the introduction of pledges or appeals to ancestors and ancestral spirits, the ritual pouring of libations, the sacrifice of live animals, and gatherings during disputes serve to formalize oaths and present cases to the elders for consideration. Consequently, the judgment or decision of the chief priest is upheld and adhered to by the parties involved in the dispute.

In Rivers State, the village General Assembly and the traditional institution, such as the council of chiefs, play a pivotal role in resolving conflicts pertaining to marital issues and communal disputes. The parties embroiled in these disputes are summoned by either the General Assembly or the council of chiefs to amicably address all matters at hand. Onigu-Otite & Olawale (2001) underscore that traditional conflict resolution processes are essential components of a well-organized and long-standing social system that seeks to promote reconciliation, uphold social bonds, and encourage progress. The probability of achieving reconciliation through traditional methods far surpasses that of conflicts resolved through legal proceedings. Onigu-Otite & Olawale (2001) further expound on the ongoing deliberations concerning ways to enhance the effectiveness of conflict prevention, management, resolution, and transformation. The focus is on formulating a comprehensive preventive action plan, encompassing strategies that are in line with the defined objectives and desired preventive outcomes.

SYNOPTIC REVIEW OF ONELGA SECURITY, PLANNING AND ADVISORY COMMITTEE (OSPAC)

The inception of the Onelga Security, Planning and Advisory Committee (OSPAC) in Nigeria marked the genesis of a local security initiative designed to combat crime and insecurity in the region. The OSPAC embodies a community-driven approach to security and peace-building, emphasizing the importance of cooperation among community members, traditional leaders, and local authorities to safeguard the well-being of the community (Emenike and Emenike, 2021). At its essence, the OSPAC epitomizes the principle of community engagement and ownership in security affairs, acknowledging the community's vested interest in upholding peace and security within their vicinity. By rallying and organizing local residents, the OSPAC aims to establish a unified front against criminal activities, enhance vigilance, and nurture a sense of collective accountability (Isurmona, 2020). One of the primary assets of the OSPAC lies in its capacity to bridge the divide between the community and law enforcement agencies, serving as a supplementary force to the prevailing security apparatus and collaborating closely with the police and other security entities. Members of the OSPAC act as an additional security layer, providing localized expertise and intelligence that can aid law enforcement in identifying and apprehending offenders (Kotze, 2020).

Maguire and King (2020) argue that community policing, exemplified by Onelga Security, Planning and Advisory Committee (OSPAC), places a strong emphasis on preventative measures and community engagement. It transcends traditional law enforcement by incorporating aspects of social intervention, counseling, and advisory services. Members of OSPAC undergo training in conflict resolution, mediation, and community outreach, enabling them to tackle underlying social issues that contribute to crime and insecurity. This comprehensive approach acknowledges that sustainable peace and security necessitate addressing the root causes of conflict and fostering an environment conducive to the well-being of all community members. The effectiveness of OSPAC relies heavily on efficient leadership and governance structures (NCPC, 2019).

The participation of traditional rulers, community leaders, and esteemed individuals serves to validate the initiative and foster trust among community members. Their involvement in offering guidance, supervision, and mediation in times of conflict is essential for upholding harmony and ensuring the enduring viability of Onelga Security, Planning, and Advisory Committee (OSPAC) (Nwankwo and Nwankwo, 2020). Nevertheless, OSPAC faces its own set of challenges and critiques. Concerns have

been expressed regarding the potential for power abuse, human rights infringements, and vigilantism. It is imperative for OSPAC to operate within the confines of the law, upholding human rights and due process. Clearly defined protocols, mechanisms for accountability, and regular training can help address these concerns and guarantee that OSPAC operates as a conscientious and law-abiding entity (Nwankwo and Umeagbalasi, 2019).

The bye-law that brought about the establishment of the Onelga Security and Planning Advisory Committee (OSPAC) was implemented in 2019 under the leadership of the then Council Chairman, Chief (AMB.) Victor Ifeanyi Odili, and the House Leader of the Legislative Council, Hon. Onyinyecchi Ile. The bye-law consists of twenty-seven (27) sections. The preamble of the ordinance highlights that the Onelga Security Planning and Advisory Committee (OSPAC) was inspired by the Rivers State neighborhood watch of 2018. The duties of the committee are outlined as follows:

i. Establishment of Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Security Planning and Advisory Committee

This section of the bye-law is responsible for the establishment of the body referred to as OSPAC under subsection (4) of Section I of the Rivers State Neighbourhood & Safety Corps Law No 8 of 2018. OSPAC is created as a corporate entity with perpetual succession and a common seal. As a corporate entity, OSPAC is granted the authority to initiate legal proceedings and be the subject of legal action in its corporate name. Additionally, this section confers upon OSPAC the ability to acquire, possess, manage, and dispose of any movable or immovable property necessary for the efficient execution of its duties. Furthermore, the existence of OSPAC as outlined in this section does not prohibit any community from establishing its own neighborhood watch program, provided that the program is officially registered with OSPAC. Consequently, OSPAC serves as a coordinating body for all uniformed Neighborhood Corps established and operating within each community in the Local Government Area.

ii. Functions of Onelga Security Planning and Advisory Committee (OSPAC)

This section of the bye-law clearly delineates the functions of the body to provide guidance for its operations. Within this section, the bye-law specifies that the body is primarily tasked with aiding the Police and other security agencies in the State to uphold Law and order. This is the primary objective behind the establishment of the neighbourhood watch, as a measure to enhance security cooperation with the officially recognized security agencies in Nigeria, primarily the Police and other entities. The neighbourhood watch is not intended to undermine the formal security agencies, but rather to support them, particularly the Police. In addition to assisting the Nigerian Police in community policing of ONELGA, the neighbourhood watch is also responsible for establishing regulations that govern the operations of the Watch Corps and any other local vigilante group within the Local Government. This implies that local security operations, which involve securing streets and compounds, must adhere to the guidelines set forth by OSPAC. Vigilante groups are typically formed by individuals, traditional leaders, and organizations seeking security to protect their neighborhoods or properties. However, this section does not prohibit these vigilante groups but rather instructs them to operate within the framework established by OSPAC.

Primarily, this section equips the body with arms that are lightweight and less potent than those utilized by the Nigerian Police. This implies that the body should refrain from possessing firearms such as AK-47, MG24, and pestles. The ordinance authorizes them to carry knives, machetes, and locally crafted weapons. Additionally, the section authorizes the body to gather intelligence on criminal activities, ongoing crimes, any suspicious behavior, and suspected criminals. They are required to provide any pertinent information on criminal activities, ongoing crimes, suspicious behavior, and suspected criminals to the Police or any other security agency. Their duties include establishing security measures against hoodlums, cult groups, and kidnapers in the Local Government Area; conducting regular motorized patrols day and night; reducing the crime rate and ensuring that every perpetrator is identified and held accountable for their actions; overseeing the arrest of every perpetrator and ensuring that justice is served. These tasks are all aimed at collaborating with the Police to engage in any other lawful activities in upholding law and order.

iii. Establishment and Composition of the Governing Hoard of the OSPAC

The third section of the bye-law delineates the organizational structure of the entity. This structure is outlined to define the governing entities of the organization that will be responsible for its corporate governance. The governing body for the OSPAC is denoted as the "Board". The Board is tasked with

the oversight and management of the OSPAC. Leading the governing body is the Chairman, a person of outstanding integrity, possessing expertise in security and relevant fields. Following the Chairman is the Legal Adviser to the Council, who serves as the principal legal counsel for the organization. The Legal Adviser handles all legal affairs pertaining to the organization. Lastly, the Chief Security Officer of the Council holds the third position in the hierarchy. Referred to as the CSO, this individual is responsible for all security operations and activities of the organization.

The body is also represented by the Nigeria Medical Association (NMA) ONELGA, responsible for overseeing the medical needs of its members. Additionally, the Nigeria Safety and Civil Defense Corps is affiliated with the organization to help maintain peace and order in the area. A representative from the Nigerian Police is involved in overseeing the daily operations of the body and providing assistance when needed. The body also includes a representative from the Director of State Security in Rivers State, as well as the Commander of the Joint Military-Task Force (JTF) within the Local Government. Moreover, there are six individuals representing the six geo-political zones of the Local Government, each with expertise in community, security, and development matters. One individual is nominated by the Council Chairman, two representatives from multinational Oil and Gas Companies operating in the area, and a Director-General/Commandant-General of the Corp also play integral roles within the organization.

iv. Appointment of Members of the Board

The fourth section of the bye-law is dedicated to assigning the authority to appoint the leader of the Board, who serves as the Chairman of OSPAC. Even though the entity is established through legislation, the power to enforce the enacted bye-laws lies with the Executive Council led by the Chairman. Therefore, the Chairman of the Council holds the exclusive authority to appoint the Chairman and members of the Board, excluding the Ex-officio members like the representatives of the Nigerian Police, the Director of State Security, the Commander of the Joint Military-Task Force (JTF), representatives of multinational Oil and Gas Companies operating in the Local Government Area, and the Director-General/Commandant-General of the Corp. Nonetheless, these appointed individuals must receive confirmation from the Legislative Council.

v. Tenure of Office

The fifth section of the document outlines the specific details regarding the duration of the members' terms on the Board of the organization. According to this section, the Chairman and regular members of the Board (excluding ex-officio members) are to serve for a period of 4 years. Additionally, they have the opportunity to be re-appointed for another term at the discretion of the Chairman. This provision ensures stability and continuity within the Board, allowing for experienced members to potentially continue their valuable contributions to the organization.

vi. Remuneration

In the sixth section of the document, there is detailed information regarding the allowances granted to the members of the Board. According to the section, individuals holding positions such as Director-General, Commandant-General, Chairman, Secretary, and other Board members will be appointed on a part-time basis. These individuals are entitled to receive sitting allowances, as well as any other allowances that the Chairman deems appropriate and approves. This provision ensures that all members of the Board are fairly compensated for their time and contributions to the organization.

vii. Cessation of Office

This section clearly outlines the circumstances under which a Board member may lose their position on the Board. Apart from resigning formally, a member can be removed from office if they are unable to fulfill their duties due to physical or mental incapacity. Additionally, being convicted of a crime, declaring bankruptcy, or engaging in serious misconduct or neglect of duty can also lead to removal from office. The Chairman of the Council is authorized to dismiss any Board member if they are found to be acting against the public interest.

viii. Meetings of the Board

This section provides detailed information on how the Board members are to convene for meetings. According to the guidelines, the Board is allowed to meet once every quarter, unless there is an emergency situation that requires an immediate meeting. This means that throughout the calendar year,

the Board is expected to convene a total of three times, excluding any emergency meetings that may arise.

In the event of an emergency or a crucial meeting that is not part of the regular schedule, the Chairman or a minimum of seven (7) Board members must submit a written request to the Chairman of the Council seeking permission to hold the meeting. The Chairman of OSPAC is responsible for presiding over the Board meetings, unless he is unavailable, in which case another member present may be nominated to lead the meeting.

For a meeting to proceed, a quorum of at least seven (7) members must be present. This ensures that there are enough members for decisions to be made and actions to be taken by the Board. By following these guidelines, the Board can effectively carry out its duties and responsibilities in a timely and organized manner.

ix. Power to Arrest

This particular provision in the bye-law outlines the operational procedures of the organization. The OSPAC, as described in this section, is granted the authority to apprehend and search individuals who engage in, assist, support, or are suspected of involvement in any criminal activities within the Local Government area. Subsequently, it is required that the individuals arrested be promptly turned over to the Police or other relevant security agencies located closest to the point of arrest. Any actions carried out by OSPAC members beyond their prescribed powers are deemed to be unauthorized.

In conclusion, the Onelga Security, Planning, and Advisory Committee (OSPAC) represents a groundbreaking and community-centered approach to security and peace-building (Nwanolue and Nwosu, 2020). By empowering local communities and fostering cooperation among residents, traditional leaders, and law enforcement agencies, OSPAC strives to tackle crime and insecurity in a holistic and enduring manner. Despite encountering obstacles, through effective governance, training, and commitment to upholding the rule of law, OSPAC has the capacity to significantly contribute to improving security, promoting peace, and elevating the standard of living in communities.

THE ROLE OF OSPAC IN SECURITY MANAGEMENT

The research inquiry (1) was formulated to examine the role of OSPAC in security management in ONELGA. ONELGA has long been recognized as an area plagued by persistent security challenges. Oke (2018) reported that the residents of ONELGA have endured significant harassment, including killings, injuries, and destruction, as a result of the actions of troublemakers, hoodlums, and criminals. The Fund for Peace (2014) documented that gang activities and other organized crimes in ONELGA resulted in the deaths of over 30 individuals from July to October. Ahakwa and Amadi (2021) affirmed that ONELGA has experienced some of the most brutal massacres and security issues in Rivers State, leading to the devastation of the region. This has caused disruptions to banks and other economic activities, resulting in the abandonment of key development projects such as the dualization of internal roadways, for example, the Omoku-Ahoadia link road.

One of the most notorious instigators of insecurity in ONELGA was the late Igwedibia Johnson, also known as Don Waney, who orchestrated acts of insecurity and chaos in the region. Don Waney and his gang have been instilling fear in the region for years, holding key economic, political, and social institutions hostage. He is considered the primary criminal responsible for the killings and property destruction in ONELGA. One of the most harrowing moments that cast a negative spotlight on the region both nationally and internationally was the massacre of 22 church members on January 1st. Following Don Waney's demise, security forces unearthed bodies buried by him and discovered additional heavy weaponry and ammunition at his residence in Omoku (Amadi, 2020).

The security challenges mentioned were the primary impetus for the creation of the ONELGA Security, Planning, and Advisory Committee (OSPAC) in 2017 by the local government, specifically aimed at addressing the activities of Don Waney and other delinquents in the area. Following the demise of Don Waney, OSPAC took action against other cult groups and associates who had been unleashed. For

instance, subsequent to the demise of Don Waney, OSPAC has persistently upheld peace and security in ONELGA by targeting cult members and drug traffickers in the vicinity (Adiele & Nwabueze, 2022). The role of the ONELGA Security and Peace Advisory Committee (OSPAC) in maintaining peace and security within the region is multifaceted, a topical issue which is the focus of this paper. One of the key functions of OSPAC in security operations within ONELGA, is to provide support to the Nigerian police, the Nigerian army, and other law enforcement agencies in security oversight. OSPAC has been collaborating with the Nigerian Police and other security agencies to ensure security within ONELGA. This alignment with the provisions of the organization's bye-law that established OSPAC further reinforces this assertion:

Under this section, the bye-law stipulates that the body would amongst other things perform first and foremost, assist the Police and any other security agency in the State to maintain Law and order. This is the prime reason for the establishment of the neighbourhood watch, as a law that would build security relations with the formally established security agencies in Nigeria, which is essentially the Police and other agencies. They are not established to topple the formal security agencies but they are only assisting these agencies especially the Police

This assertion is in line with Offor, Atei & Stanley (2020) citing Edozie (2018) revealed that:

OSPAC in November 2017 led a team of soldiers from the six (6) Division Nigerian Army who raided the residence of Don Waney the South-South Journal of Humanities and international Studies Vol.3 No.2 June, 2020 OSPAC and Crime Control in ONELGA, Rivers State 266 notorious gang leader who terrorized Omoku. During the raid, items discovered which aided his evil act included sophisticated weapons, dynamites, dozens of cannabis, military uniforms, military boot, communication radios, ten human skulls and bones (p.2).

As part of their key role of assisting the Nigerian Police and other security agencies, OSPAC aided and abetted the apprehension of the perpetrators of the New Year killings in Omoku in 2018 forced Don Waney, his second-in-command; Ikechukwu Adiele and other powerful gang member Lucky Ode to flee to Enugu, in Enugu State where they finally met their death on 8th January 2018, in a gun battle with troops from the 82 division Nigerian Army Enugu and men of the Department of State Service (DSS) from Rivers State Command in their place of refuge (Offor, Atei & Stanley, 2020).

The secondary function of OSPAC in security intervention in ONELGA, as indicated in the item, is to monitor the operations of cult factions in the area. This assertion aligns with the perspective of Offor, Atei & Stanley (2020), who stated that:

OSPAC by its formation were determined to fight the menace by checking the activities of various cult groups that threatened the inhabitants of the local government area. Popular among the cult groups were the Greenland, Islands, Deywell and Deygbam who in course of their war of supremacy made the area uninhabitable and as well crippled all social and economic activities vital for the sustenance of the people (p.4).

The third function of OSPAC in security intervention in ONELGA, as outlined in the aforementioned item, is the undertaking of rescue operations for kidnapped victims in Offor, Atei & Stanley (2020) the area. This assertion aligns with the research of Offor, Atei & Stanley (2020) citing Offor, Atei & Stanley (2020), which references Aaron (2019), who posited that...

OSPAC as an indigenous security group in ONELGA also embark on rescue operations of kidnapped victims. Such gallant effort done in collaboration with the military has members of the group leading the operation. But while on the search, if there is an attack on any criminal gang, OSPAC returns back fire on any form considered appropriate. The fourth function of OSPAC in security intervention in ONELGA, as outlined in the item, involves conducting stop and search operations at the entrance to the local government area (p.5).

This assertion is in line with Offor, Atei & Stanley (2020) which revealed that OSPAC in the exercise of their duties conduct stop and search at the entrance of the local government area. Through this approach, intending escaped criminals, cultists and other suspects were apprehended and handed over to the law enforcement agencies. Also of great significant to the method was the recovery of illegal weapons from the hoodlums who terrorized ONELGA people (p.12).

Moreover, the regional security organization, in their mission to maintain security, provides their services across the six districts of the local government, specifically Omoku, Egi, Eburu, Osomini, Ndoni, and Egbema, where their daily operations are focused on combating crime and unlawful behavior. In order to enhance security measures, despite enlisting members from each district, credible sources indicate that suspected locations or structures where weapons may be concealed are thoroughly inspected under the oversight of the security authorities.

THE CONFLICT MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES UTILIZED BY OSPAC IN CONFLICT MANAGEMENT IN ONELGA.

In order to restore peace and security in ONELGA, OSPAC has implemented several key strategies. This study focuses on research question two (2), which examines these strategies. One of the primary conflict management strategies employed by OSPAC in ONELGA is the utilization of supernatural powers. Offor, Atei & Stanley (2020) stated thus:

Again, during the period of training, newly recruited members are exposed to some traditional practices which involve the use of charms for protection. Because of the consequences attached to offenders of the traditional practices, trainees are strictly warned and advice on the rules guiding the practices of OSPAC (p.21).

The second conflict resolution strategy employed by OSPAC in ONELGA involves fostering partnerships with local vigilante groups to effectively manage conflicts. Among the three hundred and seventy-one (371) respondents surveyed, three hundred and sixty (360) confirmed OSPAC's collaboration with vigilante groups, while eleven (11) respondents disputed this claim. Thus, the prevailing consensus supports the notion that OSPAC indeed works in conjunction with vigilante groups to address conflicts in ONELGA.

The third strategy employed by OSPAC to address conflict in ONELGA involved the use of firearms. Again, Offor, Atei & Stanley (2020, p.23) revealed that “within the three weeks training new in-takes are taught how to use arms and ammunition during operation” .

This claim aligns with the findings of Offor, Atei & Stanley (2020), who stated that beneath the Protection Officer (PRO) lies the armorer, responsible for overseeing arms and ammunition. The armorer is accountable for all weapons in the armory on a daily basis, signing out and receiving arms and ammunition during and after operations. The fourth conflict management strategy employed by OSPAC in addressing conflicts in ONELGA involves conducting roadblocks and patrols. Out of the 371 respondents, 360 agreed that roadblocks and patrols are effective strategies for conflict management in ONELGA, while 11 disagreed. This indicates that the general consensus supports OSPAC's use of roadblocks and patrols in managing conflicts in ONELGA. Additionally, Offor, Atei & Stanley (2020) noted that, in order to enhance security measures, security roadblocks are strategically placed to prevent armed criminal groups and hoodlums from entering the city of Omoku and its surroundings. Furthermore, the study revealed that OSPAC does not solely rely on regular patrols to achieve optimal success in combating insecurity.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The formation of OSPAC as a vigilante group in combating conflict in ONELGA have proved a square peg in a square hole. Prior to its formation, the region was totally ungovernable and healthy living and business activities were undermined. Despite the reservations of using civilians to legally confront

insecurity, as one that could metamorphose into different causal effects such as militias and other criminal groups, the vigilante group have continually remind citizens of the essence of peace-building in community development. By adopting different strategies, the vigilante groups have become an extension of security agencies. Most notably, the use of extra mundane powers to counter the diabolic activities of criminals region have proven that insecurity is beyond human capacities. However, despite the success achieved by the vigilante group, there is still more that needs to be done for the activities of the group to be maximized, as well as avoid the vigilante group to become apposite and inimical to the same conflict they were constituted to perform. Most notably, poor funding, lack of tech know-how, constitutional impediments and political interference must be addressed by the state and local government in order to consolidate peace-building in ONELGA.

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made which are:

1. OSPAC members should be trained, educate and sensitized from time to time to enhance their role in conflict management. These training, symposiums and crusade should be organized with expert in security and conflict management from competent security agencies within and outside the country
2. OSPAC members should be availed with the best security and conflict management facilities and sophisticated equipment in order to strengthen them in their various strategies adopted in conflict management

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